

Relationship of Eating Behavior Based on Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26 with Adolescent Nutritional Status

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Abstract

Introduction: In Indonesia, the problem of malnutrition and over nutrition is a problem that still often occurs in adolescence. Many factors determine the nutritional status of adolescent, one of them is eating behavior. **Purpose:** This study aimed to analyze the relationship between eating behavior based on Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26 with nutritional status in adolescents in Islamic High School 1 Sleman Yogyakarta. **Methods:** This study was an observational study using cross-sectional design on 172 adolescent who selected by total sampling. Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26 questionnaire is at risk for eating behavior at risk. The hypotheses were tested using Kendall's tau correlations. **Results:** The results showed that the majority of adolescent had risk eating behaviors in the low category, namely as many 73(42,4%) and had nutritional status in the normal category of 84 adolescents (48,8%). This shows that the lower the risk of eating behavior, the better/normal nutritional status. The results of cross-sectional analysis have a value of $r=0,144$ and $p=0,033$ (p value =0,05). **Conclusion:** There is a relationship between eating behavior at risk with nutritional status in adolescents in Islamic High School 1 Sleman Yogyakarta.

Keywords: Eating Behaviour, Adolescent, Nutritional Status.

INTRODUCTION

The issue of nutritional status is still widely experienced by adolescents. Nutritional problems in adolescents are known as the double burden of malnutrition. The double burden of malnutrition refers to a condition where many adolescents experience both undernutrition and overnutrition. This double burden occurs in many countries, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (Gregory, 2015; Haddad et al., 2015; Setyawati & Kurniadi, 2021). Adolescent malnutrition is an evolving global issue. Behaviors acquired during adolescence often persist into adulthood, making adolescence a critical period for instilling positive eating and health behaviors (Ahmed et al., 1998; Craigie et al., 2011).

Indonesia's Basic Health Research Survey (Riskesdas) reported that 25.7% of

adolescents aged 13-15 were classified as stunted in 2018, a decrease from 35.1% in 2013. Likewise, the proportion of underweight adolescents aged 13-15 decreased from 14.1% in 2013 to 8.7% in 2018. However, the proportion of overweight or obese adolescents increased from 10% in 2013 to 16% in 2018. A similar trend occurred in older age groups. Among individuals aged 16-18, the national survey reported a decline in stunting (from 31.2% in 2013 to 26.9% in 2018) and underweight (from 19.4% in 2013 to 8.1% in 2018). On the other end of the malnutrition spectrum, overweight or obesity increased from 7.3% in 2013 to 13.5% in 2018 (Ministry of Health, Republic of Indonesia, 2018; Rachmi et al., 2016; Shrimpton & Rokx, 2013; Usfar et al., 2010).

Nutritional issues among adolescents have both immediate and

long-term negative impacts. According to Kulkarni et al. (2021), malnutrition due to nutrient deficiency, excess, or imbalance puts adolescents at high risk of developing chronic diseases (obesity, hypertension, coronary heart disease, stroke, diabetes mellitus, kidney disorders, bone disorders, etc.), especially when combined with unhealthy lifestyle behaviors. According to Devkota & Chang (2015), while nutritional problems are not usually the direct cause of death, they can weaken the immune system and make adolescents more vulnerable to fatal infections. Devi (2012) suggests that undernourished adolescents may show impaired activity, thinking abilities, social interactions, and hormonal imbalances in adolescent girls. Carroll-Scott et al. (2013) report that many studies have shown malnutrition and poor health are common causes of high absenteeism, early school dropout, and declining performance and achievement in class.

These problems arise due to multiple factors, including direct and indirect ones. Direct factors include infection and nutrient intake. Several factors influence food intake, including eating patterns, snacking behavior, nutritional knowledge, family economy (parents' occupations, food production, housing conditions, and parents' income). Indirect factors include the host, agent, and environment. Host factors include physiology, metabolism, and nutrient needs. Agent factors include nutrients, such as macronutrients (carbohydrates, proteins, and fats) and micronutrients (vitamins and minerals). Environmental factors include food materials, preparation, serving, personal hygiene, and food sanitation (Berg, 1973; Rahayuwati et al., 2019; Yan et al., 2018).

Adolescents often have their own views regarding body image, which are often incorrect. For many adolescent girls, having an ideal body is a dream, and to achieve this, many girls engage in strict

dieting, leading to imbalanced and inadequate nutritional intake. They may also consume diet pills, slimming products, herbal drinks, etc. These efforts can result in a decline in nutritional status if not done correctly, with energy and nutrient intake falling below the recommended dietary allowance (Erdenebileg et al., 2018; Niswah et al., 2021).

In Indonesia, the increasing proportion of nutritional problems among adolescents has drawn more attention to this age group. However, there has been little implementation of programs targeting adolescents; most focus on adolescent girls, specifically in Fe and folic acid supplementation. Various studies indicate that the lack of attention in recent decades has resulted in insufficient data on adolescent nutrition in Indonesia. Using evidence from other countries to inform local action is insufficient due to the significant differences between countries (Dukhi, 2020; Mbuya et al., 2019; Wiseman et al., 2018).

Based on this background, further studies are needed to identify factors that can improve adolescent nutritional status. Therefore, the author intends to conduct a study on adolescent nutritional status. The aim of this research is to examine the relationship between eating behavior, as measured by the Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26, and adolescent nutritional status.

METHODS

This study is observational or non-experimental research. The research design used is cross-sectional. The population in this study consists of all students at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta, totaling 172 students. The sampling technique used is total sampling, where the sample size is the same as the population. In this study, the sample used is adolescents in grades X and XI. The study was conducted in the classrooms of

X and XI at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta, adhering to COVID-19 prevention protocols. Data analysis was carried out using proportion tests and hypothesis tests with the Kendal-tau correlation test. The research instruments included the Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26 questionnaire and anthropometric measurements.

RESULTS

Respondent Characteristics

The respondents in this study were 172 adolescents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta. Respondents were obtained directly by the researchers and have characteristics that can be classified by age and gender. The characteristics of respondents in this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Respondents Based on Age and Gender Among Adolescents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta

Characteristic	Frekuensi	Persentase
Sex		
Woman	90	52,3
Man	82	47,7
Age		
15-16 yo	85	49,4
17-18 yo	87	50,6
Education of eating behavior		
No (never)	117	68,1
Yes	55	31,9
Infection disease in Last 1 month		
No (never)	4	2,3
Yes	168	97,7
Total	172	100

Most of the respondents had never received counseling on eating behaviors, with 117 adolescents (68.1%), and most had not been ill in the past month, with 168 adolescents (97.7%).

Risky eating behavior of adolescents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta

This analysis aims to observe the frequency distribution of risky eating behavior based on the Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26. The eating behavior of adolescent respondents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Risky Eating Behavior Based on the Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26 at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta

Risky Eating Behavior	Frekuensi	Persentase
Low	73	42,4%
Medium	43	25%
High	56	32,6%
Total	172	100%

Table 2 shows that the majority of adolescents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta have low-risk eating behavior, with a total of 73 adolescents (42.4%). The table also reveals that a significant number of adolescents exhibit medium- and high-risk eating behavior, with 56 adolescents

(32.6%) and 43 adolescents (25%), respectively.

Adolescent Nutritional Status at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta

This analysis aims to observe the frequency distribution of adolescent nutritional status at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta. The nutritional status of

adolescents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta is presented in Table 3

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of Adolescent Nutritional Status at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta

Risky Eating Behavior	Frekuensi	Percentage
Under weight	38	22,1%
Normal	102	59,3%
Over weight	20	11,6%
Obese	12	7,0
Total	172	100%

Table 3 shows that the majority of respondents, adolescents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta, are in the normal nutritional status category, with 102 adolescents (59.3%). There are also some who are categorized as obese, overweight, or underweight.

Correlation Between Risky Eating Behavior Based on Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26 and Adolescent Nutritional Status at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta

This analysis aims to determine whether there is a statistically significant relationship between risky eating behavior, as measured by the Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26, and adolescent nutritional status at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta. Statistical testing was conducted using the SPSS software to perform Crosstabulation and Kendall's Tau correlation analysis. The results of the cross-tabulation of eating behavior with nutritional status among adolescents are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Crosstabulation Analysis and Kendall's Tau Correlation Test of Risky Eating Behavior Based on Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26 with Adolescent Nutritional Status at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta

Risky Eating Behavior based on <i>Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26</i>	Nutrient status								Total	P value	R value	
	Underweight		Normal		Overweight		Obese					
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Low	15	8,7	80	46,5	2	1,2	0	0,0	97	56,4	0,033	0,413
Medium	9	5,3	13	7,6	3	1,7	3	1,7	28	16,3		
High	14	8,1	9	5,2	15	8,7	9	5,3	47	27,3		
Total	38	22,1	102	59,3	20	11,6	12	7,0	172	100		

Table 4 shows that adolescents with low-risk eating behavior tend to have normal nutritional status, with 80 adolescents (46.5%). The Kendall's Tau correlation test yielded a p-value of 0.033 ($p < 0.05$) and a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.413. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, it can be concluded that there is a statistically significant relationship between risky eating behavior and nutritional status among adolescents.

DISCUSSION

This study, conducted with 172 adolescents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta, shows that the majority of respondents exhibit low-risk eating behavior, with 73 adolescents (42.4%) falling into this category. However, there are also respondents with medium and high-risk eating behaviors, with 43 adolescents (25%) in the medium category and 56 adolescents (32.6%) in the high category. This indicates that SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta faces issues that need

to be addressed. This finding is consistent with research by Pantaleon (2019), which indicates that healthy eating behavior can be achieved by choosing nutritious and balanced foods. Healthy eating behavior is also related to recommended diets or healthy diets, such as consuming low-fat, high-fiber foods and increasing the intake of vegetables and fruits. A significant number of respondents exhibit high and medium risk for eating behavior disorders, potentially due to an obsession with being thin and fear of being overweight, as seen in questions 1 and 11 of the Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26.

According to Wulansari (2018), as long as the ideal body image is thin, many individuals are at high risk for eating behavior disorders. For adolescents, several factors contribute to eating behavior disorders, including individual, family, biological, and psychological factors. Eating behavior disorders can be harmful to physical and social health, with severe effects including body image disorders and even death. The high risk of eating behavior disorders among adolescents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta may be due to their age, as indicated in Table 4, where the majority aged 15-18 have a high obsession with weight loss through improper diets. Therefore, if many adolescents are at high risk for eating disorders, it is likely because they cannot accept their physical condition well.

Nutritional Status of Adolescents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta

The study conducted at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta shows that the majority of respondents have a normal nutritional status, as assessed by Body Mass Index (BMI), with 84 adolescents (48.8%). There are also respondents classified as underweight (53 adolescents, 30.8%), overweight (11 adolescents, 6.4%), and obese (24 adolescents, 14%). This indicates that there are still issues that need to be addressed at SMA Islam 1

Sleman Yogyakarta. According to Irianto (2014), factors affecting nutritional status include family knowledge and economic status. Higher family knowledge and economic status typically correlate with better nutritional status. Family economic status is also linked to food availability, food prices, purchasing power, and knowledge about nutrition and health. The assumption is that the higher number of respondents with normal nutritional status is due to better family knowledge and economic status, allowing families to meet nutritional needs and provide nutritious food. Nutritious food positively impacts adolescent growth and development.

This study aligns with research by Rahayuwati et al. (2019), which suggests that adolescent nutritional issues are a continuation of childhood nutritional problems, such as iron deficiency anemia and weight issues. Adolescents are quickly influenced by their environment, with unusual preferences like vegetarianism or food fadism being examples of such influence. Concerns about body image can lead to not eating, sometimes resulting in anorexia nervosa (Roza et al., 2021). The assumption is that underweight respondents may be due to excessive dieting behaviors. Adolescents may be anxious about their body image, leading to restrictive eating out of fear of gaining weight. Additionally, some may come from communities with lower knowledge and economic status, impacting their ability to meet nutritional needs, which then affects their nutritional status. The 30.8% of underweight adolescents may be due to their inability to maintain weight and adherence to incorrect diets. Various factors affect BMI, including gender and eating patterns. The 6.4% overweight and 14% obese adolescents might be due to the transitional phase of adolescence, which is crucial for forming lifestyle habits and behaviors.

Relationship Between Risky Eating Behavior Based on Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26 and Adolescent Nutritional Status at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta

Based on the study of 172 adolescents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta, the Kendall's Tau correlation analysis showed a p-value of 0.033 ($p < 0.05$) and a correlation coefficient (CC) of 0.144. This indicates a significant relationship between eating behavior based on the Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26 and nutritional status among adolescents. The results show that while some adolescents with normal nutritional status exhibit low-risk eating behavior (32 adolescents, 43.8%), others with normal nutritional status exhibit high-risk eating behavior (29 adolescents, 51.8%).

This finding is consistent with Sholikhah (2019), which found a relationship between eating behavior and nutritional status among adolescents. This view is supported by the theory that eating behavior within a group impacts the group's nutritional status. Therefore, nutritional improvement programs should promote good eating habits to support government efforts in food diversification. Poor eating habits should be replaced with new ideas to achieve better nutrition.

CONCLUSION

Based on this study, it can be concluded that there is a relationship between eating behavior based on the Eating Attitude Test (EAT)-26 and nutritional status among adolescents at SMA Islam 1 Sleman Yogyakarta ($p < 0.05$). The study indicates that individuals with poor eating behavior have a higher risk of nutritional disorders. Thus, collaboration among various parties is needed to improve adolescents' knowledge about the importance of optimal nutrition during growth and understanding of healthy diets. Future

research should explore other factors affecting adolescent nutritional status.

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